

ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS OF COLUMNAR FOUNDATIONS OF FRAME BUILDINGS

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***Abstract.** The perspective of technology of arrangement of prefabricated monolithic columnar foundations for low-rise frame structures is considered. An analysis of modern publications and existing structural and technological solutions for the construction of prefabricated and monolithic columnar foundations was carried out. Modern versions of the technology of arrangement of prefabricated monolithic columnar foundations are considered. The sequence of the device for each option is considered, taking into account the factors affecting the process. Comparison of foundations arrangement by monolithic, prefabricated and prefabricated monolithic technologies was performed. To assess the effectiveness of structural and technological solutions, criteria are defined. The list of criteria is compiled in accordance with the conditions that are present during the construction of the building, and affect the pace of construction and installation work. The analysis of existing technologies of arrangement of foundations in accordance with the criteria, as well as the main advantages and disadvantages of using structural and technological solutions. It is determined that the main disadvantage for the*

prefabricated technology is the device of connecting elements and the cost of delivering elements. The disadvantages of the monolithic technology of arranging foundations are high labor intensity and breaks for gaining concrete strength, slowing the pace of construction of the building. The result of the analysis of structural and technological solutions in accordance with the criteria is a solution that will combine the advantages of prefabricated and monolithic technologies. When considering technological solutions of prefabricated-monolithic foundations, it is determined that technological interruptions caused by the hardening of the concrete mixture can be significantly reduced, which will affect the timing of the construction of foundation structures and the frame building. Special formwork and fixing elements can be used for pre-cast foundations. The prefabricated monolithic technology of arrangement of columnar foundations considered in the article is promising for further study.

Keywords: *Frame house, prefabricated monolithic foundation, construction equipment, labor intensity, speed.*

Relevance of the problem. Frame structures are widely used in world construction practice. The speed of erection, reliability of structures, uniformity of elements, large runs inside the building, providing a lot of free space, excellent performance characteristics – durability, corrosion resistance under the conditions of proper care and selection of materials of structures in accordance with the operating conditions, these characteristics became key in finding rational design and technical solutions, what will lead to the effective use of resources in the construction.

At the current level of development of the construction industry, there are trends in the construction of frame buildings for industrial and civil purposes in the direction of mass application of frames in one to four floors. The main representatives of such buildings were logistics houses, shopping and entertainment centers, office buildings.

A characteristic constructive solution of the foundations for such houses are columnar reinforced concrete foundations mainly of a glass type. In the construction market there are various prefabricated, monolithic and prefabricated-monolithic columnar foundations, the analysis of the effectiveness of which according to the criterion of the speed of erection of the frames of buildings is absent.

Analysis of publications. The main normative documents for defining constructive decisions of foundations are the state standards of Ukraine [1, 2]. The development of structures and technologies for the construction of columnar foundations was carried out by various researchers [3, 4]. A number of construction companies in Ukraine [5, 6] and Europe [7, 8] produce prefabricated foundations. For monolithic columnar foundations, various formwork systems are offered [9, 10]. According to the results of the patent search, many interesting wine-takers that deserve to be considered [11, 12] were found. In scientific publications [13, 14] there are attempts of comparative analysis of constructive and technological solutions of foundations.

Purpose of work. To analyze the options of columnar foundations of the national team, monolithic and prefabricated monolithic structure according to the criteria of labor intensity and speed of erection of frame low-rise buildings.

Presentation of the main research material. By placement in relation to the surface of the earth columnar are assigned to the foundations of shallow laying. Columnar foundations are represented by four options: Prefabricated (F1); Monolithic (F2); (6) with a full-size band (F3). Prefabricated monolithic with a prefabricated slab and monolithic subcolumn (F4) [14].

The following evaluation criteria are selected for the analysis of the CTR of the foundations:

- Q1* – ability to perform processes in wet pit;
- Q2* – costs for transporting structures and materials to the object;
- Q3* – the need for a more powerful crane;
- Q4* – the number of technological breaks to perform a full range of actions;

Q_5 – the cost of working on the foundation and the installation of columns.

Q_6 – the impact of winter conditions on the installation of the foundation and the installation of columns.

The main parameters of prefabricated foundations (F1) depend on the size of the cross section of the columns of the first tier. In accordance with the load on the foundations of low-rise frames (10000...16000 kPa), the slab part of the foundations in the conditions of water-saturated soils will have dimensions up to 2.7 x 2.7 m (in terms of). The weight of such a foundation can reach 6.0 tons of increase in the size of the foundation is not possible due to restrictions on road and transport dimensions.

Oberbeton Plant (Zhytomyr) [6] and *Kovalska Plant* (Kyiv) [5] (Fig.1) offer a foundation glass with a plate part with the size of the plate part 1.36 x 0.5 m (under columns 0.4 x 0.4 m) and 1.5 x 1.5 m (under columns 0.5 x 1.36 m).

Fig. 1. Columnar foundation with a glass with a plate part (F1):

1 – preparation for the foundation; 2 – foundation plate (combined); 3 – a glass with a plate part; 4 – pin lock; 5 – mounted column

In cases where the area of the plate part of the glass is not enough, under the glass arrange an additional plate with dimensions of 2.1 x 2.1 m thick 350 mm or 2.4 x 2.4 m thick 400 mm. The additional plate can be monolithic if the conditions of a dry pit allow.

For the analysis of the CTR of the foundations, variants of the groundwater level were considered:

RGV-n – groundwater level below the bottom of the pit at least 0.5 m;

RGV-s – the level of groundwater above the bottom of the pit, but not above the slab share of the foundation;

RGV-B – the level of soil is located on a glass of foundation.

By options (RGV-s) and (RGV-V), only the combined plate can be used. Monolithic version of the plate 2 (see Figure 1) is possible only at the level of groundwater below the bottom of the pit (RGV-n). Relevant conclusions also relate to the arrangement of preparation for the foundation: Concrete monolithic preparation for the option (RGV-n); for other options, preparation only from crushed.

According to the criterion ($Q2$), the F1 variant is not convenient for efficient transport of structures to the object. The shape and dimensions do not allow to fully use the capabilities of road freight transport.

Installation of the foundation ($Q3$) requires a more powerful crane. Actually, under the columnar foundations, separate foundation pits are designed (between the foundations 6.0...12.0 m), the crane is selected for the departure of the arrow 16...18 m (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The scheme of installation of prefabricated elements of the foundation

According to the criterion ($Q4$) for all prefabricated elements, there is only one technological break to achieve a concrete joint of the column with a foundation of strength not less than 70% of the project ($R28$). Under normal conditions of endurance, concrete gains such strength for 5...7 days.

Labor costs ($Q5$) for the installation of the prefabricated foundation are minimal, since the number of operations (actions) of the foundation process is minimal.

The influence of winter conditions on the foundation ($Q6$) is insignificant, it is manifested only when concreting the joint of columns with foundations. You need to heat the concrete. The disadvantage of a constructive solution for excellent

temperatures is considered to be a very small amount of concrete (less than 0.1 m³), the isothermy of cement is very small. Also noted is the increased complexity of the process due to the manufacture of concrete mixture on the site in small portions.

The option of monolithic foundations (F2) with cups is practically not used, so in the subsequent analysis are not illuminated.

The main parameters of prefabricated monolithic foundations (F3) also depend on the size of the cross-section of the columns of the first tier. Characteristic parameters are the weight of the glass, and the dimensions of the monolithic plate, for the manufacture of which the formwork is already needed (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Columnar foundation (F3) with a prefabricated glass and a monolithic slab:

**1 – preparation for the foundation; 2 – monolithic plate; 3 – a combined glass;
4 – formwork panels; 5 – reinforcing nets; 6 – mounted column**

According to the criterion ($Q1$) F3 option is possible only at the level of groundwater below the bottom of the pit (RGV-n).

According to the criterion ($Q2$), the F3 variant is also not convenient for efficient transportation of structures to the object. The prefabricated glass is made of reinforcement and support tubes, therefore, the transportation process should be carried out very carefully – reinforcing releases upwards.

Installation of the prefabricated glass requires a crane of less load capacity. The weight of the cup does not exceed 1.5 tons, for example, if the F1 version requires a crane LTM 1040, then for the F3 variant – LTM 1030.

Laying concrete mixture is better to perform directly from the concrete mixer or with the help of a concrete pump.

To analyze the F3 variant by criterion (*Q4*), the structure of the construction process was considered:

1. Installation of concrete preparation with a thickness of 100 mm from heavy concrete class C10/15;
2. Exposure to concrete to a set of strength of at least 50% of R28;
3. Installation of a prefab glass on a concrete preparation by a crane;
4. Reinforcement of the sole of the foundation with a grid by hand with individual 16A400S rods with a mesh screen 100 x 100 mm;
5. installation of inventory formwork from shields and horseshoes;
6. Laying concrete mixture (concrete class C25/30) in the formwork of the foundation slab;
7. Exposure of concrete foundation slab to a strength of 70% of R28.
8. Dismantling of the formwork at the strength of concrete 30% of R28;
9. Installation and temporary fixing of columns of the first tier with wedges in cups of foundations;
10. Laying the joints of columns with foundations concrete mixture (concrete class C25/30 with rubble up to 10 mm in diameter);
11. The aging of concrete in the joints to a strength of 70% of R28 and the continuation of the process of installation of the rigels and slabs of the frame of the building.

The conditions of hardening of concrete depend on the external temperature. At an external air temperature + 20 ° C there are the following technological breaks: The first break of 4 days (50% of R28); друга і третя – по 7 дн (70% від R28).

Labor costs ($Q5$) for the installation of a prefabricated cup increase, since during the stropovannu and lifting, a turn of the glass is required and the installation on the supports on 4 legs, which complicates the process. For the installation of a monolithic plate, labor costs are increased during the installation of a reinforcing mesh of individual rods. It is possible to use reinforcing nets of factory production under the condition of transferring the process of installation of the prefabricated glass after installation of reinforcing nets. This transfer speeds up the process of arranging the foundation.

The influence of winter conditions on the foundation ($Q6$) is significant, manifested in the concreting of the foundation plate and when concreting the joint of the columns with the foundations. You need to heat the concrete. The disadvantage of a constructive solution for excellent temperatures is also considered to be a very small volume of concrete (less than 0.1 m³).

Option F4 is characterized by another sequence of monolithic and prefabricated foundation particles: A glass of foundation is formed after the installation of columns (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Columnar foundation (F4) with a prefabricated slab and monolithic glass:

1 – preparation for the foundation; 2 – combined foundation plate; 3 – reinforcement frame of the base glass; 4 – contactor-formwork; 5 – anchor fastening of the conductor; 6 – mounted column; 7 – jacks for the alignment and consolidation of the column; 8 – monolithic concrete glass foundation

By criterion (*Q1*), the F4 variant does not depend on the level of groundwater. Crushed stone preparation and installation of the foundation plate can be carried out even in water. The upper part of the foundation (glass) can be performed when pumped out water from the space of the conductor-formwork with the mandatory use of airtight gaskets under the conductor boards.

According to the criterion (*Q2*) F4 version is better than others because flat prefabricated slabs can be folded into a stack with the achievement of the greatest load of transport. The size of the plates is limited by the dimensions of transport and road restrictions. It is recommended to take sizes of plates no more than 2.7 x 2.7 m.

Installation of a combined plate requires a crane of greater load capacity. The mass of the plates can reach 9 t.

For option F4 only one technological break during the set of concrete glass foundation strength not less than 30% of *R28*. At the endurance of concrete under normal conditions, only 1 days are required.

When using the F4 variant, the device of columnar foundations with simultaneous installation of columns is expected to obtain the effect (acceleration of the process) due to the fact that, according to other options, the break for the aging of concrete preparation, soles and joints to the desired strength suspends the process of laying foundations and mounting columns, and according to the option F4, the break for the aging of concrete does not stop the process of installing structures and affects only the process of disassembling conductors with formwork.

According to the F4 option, it is possible to combine the technological flows of mounting columns, beams and slabs and the device of monolithic cups of foundations. The term of the technological break will be 1 days, but it does not affect the beginning of the installation of columns. The hardening of concrete glass of the foundation and care for concrete continues after the removal of the conductor-formwork, but this process will be carried out in parallel with the construction of the frame of the building.

Conclusions and perspectives for further development. Analysis of existing structural and technological solutions columnar foundations of frame low-rise buildings showed that the F4 option is promising and allows to speed up the process of building with a decrease in technological breaks for the endurance of monolithic foundations, respectively, and with a decrease in labor costs for these processes.

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